

ANDIJAN WAS CONQUERED BY YARKENT KHAN?**Musayev Azizbek**

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Anntonation: This article is about the political situation of the Bukhara Khanate under the Ashtarkhanid dynasty and its relations with the Yorkent Khanate and the role of the Ferghana Valley in it. The march of Yorkent Khan Abdullah Khan to the Ferghana Valley was studied through a comparative analysis of source literature.

Key words: and phrases: Khanate of Bukhara, Ashtarkhanids, Abdulaziz Khan, Yorkent Khanate, Koshgar, Kyrgyz, Osh, Andijan

From the first years when the administration of the Bukhara Khanate was transferred to the Ashtarkhanid dynasty, an active foreign policy was carried out. In the case of Khurasan, the Safavids, the Baburis for the Balkh region, and the Kazakhs for the possession of the Tashkent and Syrdarya basins had to fight constantly.

In addition, there were certain conflicts with the Yorkent Khanate over the ownership of the territories in the Fergana Valley, which is the eastern border of the Khanate. This conflict, which began during the Shaibani period, intensified during the second half of the Ashtarkhanid reign. During the reign of the ruler of Bukhara, Abdulaziz Khan (1645-1681), as a result of increasing internal disputes and increasing attacks on the khanate by the Khans of Baburi and Khorezm, the attention to the Ferghana Valley decreased a little. And this was very favorable for Yorkent Khan Abdullah Khan (1638-1667). Sultan Said Khan (1514-1533), the founder of the Yorkent Khanate, fought for the Ferghana Valley with the Shaybanites for a long time and left the area after being defeated. Later, his descendants, who rule in Eastern Turkestan, considered the valley as the property of the Chigatai clan as their centuries-old heritage. However, none of the rulers of Yorkent Khanate from Sultan Said Khan to Abdullah Khan marched directly to Ferghana. The difficult situation in the Bukhara Khanate created favorable conditions for Yorkent Khan Abdullah Khan to occupy the valley. His march to Ferghana can be studied in four stages

The first stage is 1641-1642. In the first years of his reign, he raised an army against the Kalmyks, and in 1640-1641 against the Kyrgyz in the regions of Bolor and Badakhshan [2: 196]. The author of "Tarixi Koshg`ar " Abdullah Khan noted that after conquering Bolor he marched on the Kyrgyz and defeated them

at the Norin River. But in the next battle in Aksoy, the Yorkentians suffered heavy losses [7: 111-112].

Shah Mahmud Churos, unlike the previous historian, describes this march in more detail. Abdullah Khan sent an army gathered from Aksuv, Uch, Kusan, and Bay regions under the leadership of Qazi Shah Yusufkhoja to attack the Kyrgyz. He went to Andijan. Unfortunately, the sources do not clearly record when this march took place. Based on the fact that the Bolor campaign lasted for three months, it can be said that the Andijan campaign took place in 1641-1642. Because we talked about the Kyrgyz march to Andijan in early 1642. Most likely, the pressure of the Khan of Yorkent caused them to march towards the valley. Abdullah Khan entered Osh through Shart and Osh pass [8: 197; 4: 110]. Despite the fact that the Osh people surrendered without a fight, Abdullah Khan organized a massacre here and returned. The army led by Shah Yusufkhoja was defeated in the battle with the Kyrgyz [8: 198; 2: 197; 4: 110]. It seems that the purpose of Abdullah Khan's campaign was to attack the Kyrgyz on the eastern borders and plunder some cities in the east of the Ferghana Valley. But the khan's march to Andijan failed, and he contented himself with looting Osh and returned back. The second stage took place in 1653. This time, Abdulla Khan started his second march to Andijan with all the emirs under his command. Through Osh, the Yorkent army of forty thousand people reached the city of Andijan [8: 202; 7: 110]. The army led by Khan is located near the Khagan Gate, while the Koshghar troops led by his son Yolbarskhan and his father Shahbozbek are located near the Mirza Gate. Abdullakhan settled on Gultepa Hill near the Khagan Gate and began to control the movement of the army from there. One of the emirs of the Khotan army, Mirza Yunus, was killed in one of the battles [8: 202-203]. This increases the desire to take revenge on those in the Yorkent army. As a result of the battles, the defenses at Khaqan and Mirza gates were breached and the city was stormed. After Andijan was looted for three days, Abdullah Khan decided to return. As a result of this campaign, the cities of Andijan and Osh were included in the Yorkent Khanate.

The third stage was implemented in 1654. Soon after Abdullah Khan returned, the people of Andijan refused to obey. This caused the khan to march for the third time. According to "Tarixi Koshg'ar", it is stated that this march took place one year later [7: 110]. Judging from the second and third campaigns, it can be concluded that Andijan was part of the Yorkent Khanate for a year. Abdullah Khan's troops were joined by New Hisar troops and Kyrgyz under the leadership of Yolbars Khan chief Koshghar and Sotimbek [8: 203; 4: 111]. As

before, they headed towards the valley through Shart pass. Soon Abdullah Khan came to Andijan and began to trap it. As in the previous campaign, Khan plans to settle on Gultepa Hill and enter the city through Khaqan Gate. The people of Andijan sent Botakaro father, Murad devanbegi, Kara Suyunch father, and Jomtok father to the khan in order to save time and bring the population to the full arch [8: 203]. The local population, who made good use of the negotiation process, managed to fully enter the fortress and prepare for defense. When Abdullah Khan realized the futility of negotiation, he arrested the above officials and started an attack on the city. When the Yorkentians occupied the city a year ago, they looted the city and treated the people rudely. In the work "Tarix", the residents stated that they strongly defended the city [8: 204]. After his efforts were unsuccessful, Abdullah Khan had to go back.

In 1667, Yorkent Khan Abdullah Khan's fourth march to the Ferghana Valley began. His son Nuriddin Khan fought against the Kalmyks for a long time and gained a lot of attention in the khanate, and at this year's meeting he suggested to his father to attack Andijan. Nuriddin Khan's proposal was accepted by all the participants and his father. When the army arrived in Sarigyozy region, Nuriddin Khan suddenly fell ill and died. This unexpected event forced Abdullah Khan to turn back [8: 221; 4: 117; 2: 208-209]. Thus, only the second and third of the four attacks of the Yorkent khanate to annex Andijan took place in the immediate vicinity of the city. The second attack ended successfully, and the city was temporarily annexed to the Khanate of Yorkent. This dependence did not last even a year, and a third attack was organized because he was released. As a result of the battles, the people of Andijan kept their independence. The last attack did not end like the first one.

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